

VAAC Operational Dispersion Model Configuration Snap Shot

Version 1

November 2012

Introduction

The VAACs are responsible for producing volcanic ash cloud analysis and forecasts to assist the aviation community in planning their operations and minimising risk. This function requires that the VAACs fuse volcanic activity and cloud observations, numerical weather prediction data and dispersion models and associated science within the process of producing the advisory.

The volcanic ash advisory consists of an analysis (T+0) and 18 hours of forecast. In recent times the aviation community has also requested, in an ad-hoc manner, that the VAACs or their supporting organisations provide longer-range forecasts out to T+24, T+36 and further.

Forecasting naturally requires the use of models. All VAACs use highly complex dispersion models to provide the basis of the forecast guidance that they issue. This note is intended to act a snap shot in time of the operational configuration of the VAAC dispersion models. This is therefore NOT and should NOT be used as guide to actual model capability as operational demands i.e. lack of reliable information dictate that certain functionality not be used.

For clarity the model set-up's are presented in a series of tables. It is however noted that the table format may limit the scope to explain more complex aspects. To aid in this there is a short description of certain elements preceding the tables, however for a full model description the reader is directed to the wider literature and documentation that is available.

Background

These tables were first compiled as part of the VAAC Best Practice process for the VAAC 'Inputs and Outputs' Modelling Workshop held at NCEP, Washington in November 2012.

Version 1 (Nov 2012) of this 'Snap Shot' document is an extract from the full Workshop report.

This document and these tables will be periodically updated, as part of the VAAC Best Practice process with the aim of stimulating discussion on operational practice and model utilisation.

Current Operational Modelling Configuration

All VAACs, listed below, provided detailed written descriptions of their current operational modelling configurations.

1. London VAAC
2. Washington VAAC
3. Anchorage VAAC
4. Montreal VAAC
5. Buenos Aires VAAC
6. Darwin VAAC
7. Toulouse VAAC
8. Tokyo VAAC
9. Wellington VAAC

Current Model Operational Configurations

This section contains tables summarising the VAAC's current **operational** model settings.

In order to present this information in such a concise form then 'default' or 'typical' settings may have been used. Where practical, note has been made where more 'advanced' operational user options are possible.

Preceding the tables are some brief notes summarising observations made during the workshop regarding these current VAAC settings. These notes are not exhaustive and should be considered along with the main body of this report. They are included here as a factual record of comments made by attendees at the workshop.

Source Characterisation

- VAAC Toulouse use 4x4 grid boxes to define the horizontal extent of the volcanic source. Mass is distributed in a non-uniform way across these 16 grid cells e.g. in light winds they use a Gaussian distribution with maximum mass directly above the vent location. Despite this distribution it was observed by the meeting that a source measuring 200 km (each grid cell is 0.5x0.5 degree ~ 50 km) across seemed very large. Specific concerns were raised regarding, but not limited to, small eruptions (e.g. Etna) or eruptions near to airports (e.g. Iceland) where the source size could may result in significant impacts.

Species

- Species type; gas or particulate:
 - VAAC Darwin model volcanic ash as a gas.
 - VAAC Montreal, as default, model volcanic ash as a non-sedimenting particle.
 - Consensus of the workshop was that using a gas was not best practice as it prevented such mechanisms as the interaction between sedimentation and wind shear which was seen as a very important component of forecast accuracy.
 - Questions were also asked regarding how wet deposition would be applied as wet deposition of gases and particulates is very different.

Particle Size Distribution (PSD)

- It was noted that several VAACs used PSD consisting of 4 or 6 bins while others use many bins (Tokyo) or a continuous function (Wellington).
- It was noted that the range of particle sizes used by VAAC Washington (0.6-20 microns) was rather narrow and may impact on results.
- The consensus of the workshop was that 80 bins was more detail than was probably justified by the observations of air borne ash and also by the impact that such discretisation was likely to have on the simulations.
- The workshop also wondered if 4 or 6 bins were enough to capture the distributions accurately enough.
- The workshop expressed interest in the benefit of having different PSD for different volcanic eruption types.
- The workshop therefore noted that further evaluation of PSDs and their representation in models was warranted.

Numerical Weather Prediction data (NWP):

- Vertical resolution in NWP was identified as potentially having a significant impact on dispersion forecasts through correct representation, for example, of inversions and vertical wind shear. Average vertical resolutions (height divided by number of levels) varied from ~500 m to ~2500 m. Given that NWP data typically requires several grid lengths to resolve atmospheric features the workshop felt that the VAAC researchers needed to consider if increased resolutions might be possible.

- The vertical extent of NWP data available to the VAACs varies considerably (~16 km up to ~60km). The workshop discussed the fact that WNP data needed to extend to altitudes suitable to cover most eruption scenarios. The consensus of the workshop was that 30 km represented a sensible pragmatic choice and covered all flight levels. The workshop acknowledged that eruptions to greater altitude are also possible.
- NWP horizontal resolution was also identified as a potential issue for certain eruptions e.g. small eruptions and in areas of complex terrain and shear in atmosphere e.g. Central/South America where terrain alters flow at/above summit of volcanoes.
 - GFS data used by Washington, Anchorage and Wellington VAACs at 1 degree resolution was highlighted as not being high enough to be considered best practice. GFS data is available at higher resolutions.
- The workshop discussed the potential advantage and challenges of VAACs having access to multiple NWP data sets that would enable the 'best' NWP data to be selected.
- The workshop noted that the NWP modelling domain used by Buenos Aires VAAC did not extend to the full extent of their VAAC region. BA were asked to outline their plans on dealing with this issue. The workshop did discuss potential modelling options e.g. use of nested NWP data sources.

Processes

- Use of wet deposition within dispersion model forecasts was discussed.
- The workshop recommended that wet and dry deposition loss processes should be used as default.
- Uncertainty in precipitation was identified but the benefits in more representative forecast were considered far greater than any uncertainty.
- Non-sphericity – not seen as having a significant impact for sub 100 micron particles
- Sedimentation was identified as important due to importance of vertical position in relation to wind shear. The workshop recommended that sedimentation along with appropriate PSD and ash density should be used as a default modelling option.

Source Characterization

Source term	London	Darwin	Buenos Aires	Montreal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Washington + Anchorage	Wellington
Horizontal location at source	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Typically estimated from satellite imagery	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	A list of known volcanoes, but can be varied	Smithsonian Institution. Can be varied.	List of known volcanoes. Can be varied
Horizontal dimensions/ geometry at source	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 0$	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 0$	Grid node	Diameter = 1 km or estimated from satellite imagery	Diameter = 0.4 x height above crater.	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 2$ deg. 4 x 4 grid cells used with non-uniform horizontal distribution.	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 0$	$\Delta x = \Delta y = 0$
Ability to add in a distal 'plume' as a source	No	Manual delineation of distal ash cloud used to initialize dispersion model. Includes definition of polygon boundaries, base and top.	No	No	When volcanic ash is detected from satellite image, a polygon drawn manually is used as horizontal geometry at the top of the ash.	No	Modelled ash may be horizontally moved or removed.	No
Bottom of source at volcano	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution.	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution.	Suzuki distribution used as default (Summit height)	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution.	Crater $\geq 3,000$ source bottom = crater; Crater $< 3,000$ m & source top $\geq 10,000$ m, source bottom = 5,000m; Crater $< 3,000$ m and source top $< 10,000$ m, the bottom = 1,000m.	Height of the vent. May be edited.	Height of the vent taken from Smithsonian Institution. May be edited.	Height of the vent. May be edited.
Top of source	Based on observations	Based on observations	Based on observations	Based on observations	Based on observations	Based on observations	Based on observations	Based on observations
Vertical distribution	Uniform	Uniform	Uniform, Suzuki, buoyant plume model	Uniform	Suzuki distribution. Uniform for manual cloud ?	Uniform	Uniform	Uniform
Emitted parameter	Fraction of MER (g/hr) from Mastin	MER of unit 1	Total MER (g/hr)	Total MER from Sparks et al. (1997) or Mastin et al. (2009)	Total mass specified according to fourth power of plume height and duration	Total MER (g/hr)	MER of unit 1 (total)	No mass. Number of Lagrangian particles specified.
Multiple Eruption phases	Yes	No	Yes	No (Yes)	No	Yes?	Yes	Yes (using restart)

Species Properties

Species Information	London	Darwin	Buenos Aires	Montreal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Washington + Anchorage	Wellington
Particulate (P) or Gas (G)	P	G	P	P	P	P	P	P
Single size (S), Particle Size Distribution (PSD)	PSD	N/A	PSD	N/A; S, PSD	PSD	S, PSD	PSD	PSD
PSD range (micro metres)	0.1-100	N/A	Multiple. Based on eruption type.	N/A; Several options	0.1-100	0.1 - 100	0.6-20	Log normal: mean = 10
Number of bins	6	N/A	Multiple. Based on eruption type.	N/A; Several options	80	6	4	Continuum
Density (kg/m ³)	2300	N/A	Multiple. Based on eruption type.	N/A; 2500	1100-2400 ¹	2300	2500	2000
Non-Sphericity	No	N/A	Yes	N/A; No	No	No	No	No

Greyed out text indicate user selectable but non-default options.

Montreal VAAC's default option is to model volcanic ash as a non-sedimenting particle (i.e. is not subject to gravitational settling) Several default characteristic are therefore marked as N/A as they are not applicable in this situation. Montreal VAAC are able to model, as user selectable options, a number of particle characteristics and these are indicated in grey.

¹ Dependent on particle size.

NWP Data Used by VAAC Dispersion Models

	London	Darwin	Buenos Aires		Montreal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Washington + Anchorage	Wellington
NWP data source name	MetUM	ACCESS-G, ACCESS-T	ETA/SMN	WRF-ARW/SHN-SMN	GEM-REG (regional mode); GEM-GLB (global mode)	JMA GSM	ARPEGE; IFS	GFS/GDAS; NAM; NAMA	GFS
Temporal resolution used (hours)	3	3	3	3, 1 option	3, 1 option	3	6	3	6
Horizontal resolution (Lon,Lat)	0.352, 0.234 deg	0.375, 0.375 deg	25 km	~ 24 km	~ 10; ~33 km	0.1875, 0.1875 deg	0.5, 0.5 deg	1.0, 1.0 deg; 12; 45 km	1.0, 1.0 deg
Horizontal extent (Global, Regional)	G	G; R	R	R	R; G	G	G	G; R; R	R
Vertical levels used	59	29	38	38	25 (80 possible)	60	15	23; 26; 26	12
Max altitude	30 km asl	0.1 hPa (~60 km)	25 hPa (~30 km)	5 hPa (~40 km)	~21 km; (~64 km)	0.1 hPa (~60 km)	100 hPa (~16 km)	20 hPa (~ 27 km); 50 hPa; 50 hPa (~21 km)	10 hPa (~ 30 km)
NWP forecast length (hours)	144	120	120	72 (Run at 00 UTC)	48, optional 54; 144, optional 240	84	84; 84 or 180	384; 48; 36	72
Update frequency (hours)	12	12	12	24	6; 12	6	12	6	6

Dispersion Model Processes

	London	Darwin	Buenos Aires	Montreal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Washington + Anchorage	Wellington
Dispersion model name	NAME III	HYSPLIT	Fall3D	MLDP0	JMA GATM	MOCAGE Accident	HYSPLIT	PUFF-UAF (2.1.2)
Wet deposition	Yes	No	No	Yes (In cloud only)	Yes (In cloud only)	Yes	Yes	No
Sedimentation	Yes	N/A	Yes	No; Optional	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Gravitational settling	Reynolds no. + Cunningham	N/A	Terminal (Ganser 1993)	N/A; Stokes	Terminal	Stokes	Stokes + Cunningham	Stokes
Dry deposition	Yes	No	Yes	Yes; Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Aggregation	No	N/A	No	N/A; No	No	No	No	No
Non-Sphericity	No	N/A	Yes	N/A; No	No	No	No	No
Vertical winds	NWP	NWP	NWP	NWP	NWP	NWP	NWP	Divergence

Greyed out text indicate user selectable but non-default options.

Dispersion Model Outputs

	London	Darwin	Buenos Aires	Montreal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Washington + Anchorage	Wellington
Resolution	40 km	0.2 deg	12 km	2-50 km	N/A	0.5 deg	0.25 & 0.1 deg	N/A
Vertical layers	22 x 25FL deep layers (From 000 to FL550)	Layers in m. Approx: FL000-200, 200-350, 350-550, 550-800, 000-550	2D slice at: FL50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300	FL - several	Particle location (x, y, z) plots	15 pressure levels + FL000-200, 200-350, 350-550	3 layers in m. Approx: FL000-200, 200-350, 350-550.	Particle location plots, colours every 5000 ft
Exact FL	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No (grid level approximation)	No	No
Quantity	g/m3, g/m2	g/m3	g/m3, g/m2	g/m3; g/m2	N/A	g/m3	g/m3	N/A
Standard plotting projections	lat/lon - cylindrical		lat/lon - cylindrical	Orthographic	Polar	lat/lon - Cartesian linear	Dependent on volcano latitude	lat/lon - cylindrical
Standard forecast length (hours)	120	30	72	72	18	84 - 180	48	72
Time interval	6 (3 hourly for first 9 hours)	3 (variable)	1	3 (Variable)		6	1, 6 & 12	1 (Variable)
Time Ave (hours)	6 ending at valid time	1	0	3 ending at valid time (Same as output interval)	N/A (0)	0	1 ending at valid time	N/A (0)
Model update frequency (re-run of dispersion model)	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 hourly	6 hourly

Greyed out text indicate user selectable but non-default options.

Computational Details

	London	Darwin	Buenos Aires	Montreal	Tokyo	Toulouse	Washington + Anchorage	Wellington
Run time	30 mins	~1 min	30 mins	5-10 mins	5 mins	20-25 mins	~ 10 mins	Seconds
Forecast length (hours)	120	48	72	72	18	84	48	72
Platform	x86 Linux	Sun Solar	x86 Linux	IBM Power 7	NAPS	NEC SX9	IBM AIX	x86 Linux
Parallel	Yes	?	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Cores	12	?	12	1	1	6	8	1

Model run times extrapolated for a 10 member ensemble.

Run time	~ 5 hr	~ 10 min	~ 5 hr	~ 1.5 hr	~ 1 hr	~ 4 hr	~ 1-1.5 hr	~ 2 min
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Model run times vary depending on a number of factors including forecast duration and other model configuration options. The table above reports the current forecast duration and associated model run times at each of the centers. Due to the wide range of settings these times are not directly comparable. The ensemble times are a simple extrapolation of these times and are provided as a very crude indication of the increasing computer resource requirements that ensemble approaches may require. Decisions on exact ensemble forecast duration, number of members, model configurations and the ability to run multiple models simultaneously will mean that elapsed times vary considerably from those arrived at through such a simple extrapolation.

